

A6

[06]

**EPIDEMIOLOGICAL INSIGHTS: HEPATITIS B PREVALENCE AMONG
PREGNANT FORCIBLY DISPLACED MYANMAR NATIONALS IN A ROHINGYA
CAMP OF BANGLADESH**

Ahamed MS^{1*} and Chaklader T²

¹ *Nutrition research Department, Research Physician, icddr,b , Bangladesh*

² *Department of community medicine, Dhaka community medical college, Bangladesh*

**shakilarafat76@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

Hepatitis B is a viral infection that affects the liver and causes both acute and chronic diseases. This study aimed to find out the prevalence of Hepatitis B among the pregnant women of Forcibly Displaced Myanmar National people. A rigorous cross-sectional study conducted at the Maternal and Child Health Care Centre in Balukhali camp 9, Ukhiya, Cox's Bazar, Bangladesh examining the prevalence of Hepatitis B infection among pregnant women in the Forcibly Displaced Myanmar National's camp. The investigation, involving 465 subjects, employed a comprehensive approach, encompassing interviews, laboratory investigations using the HbsAg strip test by ICT method, and meticulous data analysis. The study revealed a notable 11.40% prevalence of Hepatitis B among pregnant women in this displaced population. Demographically, a substantial proportion of affected individuals fell within the 16-20 age range, indicating a specific vulnerability among young mothers. Furthermore, the high prevalence intersected with a concerning 32.90% illiteracy rate among the respondents, highlighting the intricate relationship between educational disparities and health outcomes in displaced settings. Noteworthy gaps in knowledge were identified, with only a marginal percentage of respondents being aware of their Hepatitis B status. The study brought to light the intricate dynamics of interfamilial transmission, as 4.52% of pregnant women with Hepatitis B had a positive partner or family member. Equally alarming was the finding that 79.14% of pregnant women had not received Hepatitis B vaccination, underscoring a critical deficiency in preventive measures. The implications of these findings extend beyond immediate health concerns, emphasizing the persistent risk of mother-to-child transmission during childbirth and the perpetuation of the Hepatitis B cycle within the Forcibly Displaced Myanmar National community. This research contributes valuable insights to the academic discourse on health in displaced populations, shedding light on the multifaceted challenges faced by pregnant women. The identified factors contributing to the high Hepatitis B prevalence include a complex interplay of socio-economic determinants, encompassing poverty, limited educational opportunities, and insufficient healthcare infrastructure. The urgency of targeted interventions is underscored, necessitating a comprehensive approach that integrates healthcare, education, and preventive strategies to effectively address the root causes of Hepatitis B prevalence within this marginalized community.

Keywords: Hepatitis B, pregnant women, displacement, vaccination, prevalence